

LASER WELDING MODELLING FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTED MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION METHOD

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1 Introduction

Thermoplastic composite parts are currently developing in the composite industry. Those materials offer good mechanical strength as well as better impact resistance than for thermoset composite structures. Development of thermoplastic composites parts also requires developing adapted assembly processes that would show reliability, repeatability and possible automation. Laser welding process is a good candidate to answer those considerations.

2 Thermoplastic laser welding

Welding is a well known assembly technique that applies to a wide range of materials, as long as a melting temperature can be reached. Thermoplastic materials are among those materials, so welding techniques should also apply to thermoplastic composites. Laser welding, among other welding techniques (Infra red welding, resistive or inductive welding...) has the advantage of being a non contact technique, that can easily be automated, and that does not require the addition of an intrusive conductive material at the welding interface [1,2].

However, due to the presence of fibers, short long or continuous, at a non negligible volume fraction level, propagation of the laser energy through the composite is not as straightforward as in an homogeneous material. Presence of fibers induces

diffusion of the laser beam, diminishing the laser efficiency as the amount of fibers increases. Diffusion also depends on the fiber orientation, involving an unbalanced laser spot on the welding interface.

3 Assembly process modeling

Modeling of the laser welding of thermoplastic glass fiber composite bed is considered here. The study takes into account the microstructure of the composite in order to evaluate changes in local energy absorption and diffusion directly linked with the local fiber volume fraction value and the fiber orientation (woven or UD fabric). Modelling of the welding process is developed from the representation of the moving laser beam. The beam propagation through the composite thickness is considered thanks to the ray tracing method [3,4]. The resulting energy profile developed at the welding interface is represented in Fig. 1 for different substrate thicknesses with the same material characteristics (heat conductivity, fiber volume fraction, reflective indices) and process parameters (laser beam intensity, and time of exposure) [5]. According to the structure considered, the laser quality will differ, requiring to conduct simulations in order to avoid trial and error experimental procedures. In a further step, the modeling can be used for welding optimization

considering the energy used and the welding velocity, or the number of weld seams to produce.

Fig. 1 Resulting laser beam energy profile through composite substrate thickness

4 Material characterization

The welding quality at the interface depends on the temperature reached, that should be at least above the polymer melting temperature, but also on the viscosity of the melted mass generated. The shape, aesthetics and mechanical behaviour of the resulting assembly will depend on the local effective viscosity. Viscosity depends on the polymer characteristics, but also on the local presence of the fibers. Variability on the seam line is thus expected.

The local polymer rheology is defined through the resultant temperature profile obtained at the interface [6].

In order to accurately predict the energy transferred at the interface, characterization of the laser beam itself and of the absorbent and diffusive properties of the studied materials is conducted. Validity of the model and of the characterization procedure is then shown on real assembly structures.

References

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